

EFFECT OF PLY THICKNESS AND COOLING RATE ON DAMAGE IN THERMOPLASTIC CROSS-PLY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In this work we look at the effect of constraint ratio (geometrical factor) and cooling rate (material properties factor) on mechanical behavior and damage of cross-ply laminates made of impact-resistant Polypropylene Copolymer reinforced with continuous E-glass fibers. Two types of tensile testing were implemented: direct and load-unload. Macroscopic mechanical behavior was observed in terms of Stress-Strain relation and compared for three constraint ratios and two cooling rates.

1 INTRODUCTION

For several decades thermoset based continuous-fibre composites dominated high impact structural applications. However, in the recent years thermoplastic composites are gaining momentum due to their advantages such as lighter weight, higher impact resistance, faster production cycle, and recyclability. At the top of the list of low cost thermoplastics is Polypropylene.

Polypropylene (PP) is a semi-crystalline thermoplastic, with crystallinity and microstructure that depend on the manufacturing process, especially the cooling rate. Early studies on homopolymer PP composites showed a clear effect of cooling rate on crystallinity and eventually macroscopic mechanical performance of continuous glass-fibre reinforced Polypropylene [1].

Impact-resistant Polypropylene is usually developed by adding Polyethylene-Polypropylene copolymer to the original PP homopolymer. PE-PP copolymer is a rubbery material that is almost amorphous except for a very limited PE crystallization at the centre where PE has highest concentration [2].

It is commonly accepted that transverse cracking is one of the most critical damage mechanisms in continuous fiber-reinforced plastics. It leads to failure directly by causing fracture, or indirectly by initiating another damage mechanism e.g. delamination [3]. Damage behavior is found to be influenced by the geometrical configuration including plies ratios and boundary conditions [4], and by the properties of the matrix material and the matrix-fiber interface [5]. While there had been some studies on fracture toughness of Glass-fiber reinforced PP homopolymer and its dependence on cooling rate [3,6], there is a need for more understanding of damage behavior in composites based on thermoplastic matrices that are more complex than the basic homopolymer.

This early stage work focuses on the trends of macroscopic behaviour of the composite with respect to constraint ratio and cooling rate, paving the way for a more sophisticated research about the effect of these factors on damage initiation and progression on the microscopic level. For the time being, damage observation is based only on stiffness degradation during the load-unload testing.

2 MATERIAL AND SAMPLE PREPARATION

The material being studied here is a commercial grade impact Polypropylene reinforced with E-Glass fibres. Bonding between matrix and fibres is improved by sizing the fibres with Amino-Silane and grafting the PP with Maleic Anhydride. Alpha-nucleating agent is added to accelerate crystallization. In addition, another additive is introduced for thermal stability.

The composite is provided by the producing company in the shape of a roll of 110 [mm] wide tape, with tape thickness of 0.25 [mm]. The nominal volume fraction of E-Glass fibre is 45%.

Cross-ply laminates are produced in a custom-made mould by stacking the desired number of tapes in 0 and 90 degrees orientation and consolidating them under pressure of 7.3 [bar] and heat as per the programs illustrated in Figure 1 (left). Two cooling rates are used; fast 22 C/min and slow 3 C/min, to produce laminates with different crystallinities. Crystallinity of the resulting laminates is measured to be 43.1% for fast cooling and 48.7% for slow cooling.

To study the effect of ply thickness we chose three layup configurations: $[0/90]_s$, $[0/90_4]_s$, and $[0_4/90]_s$. The configuration $[0/90]_s$ is taken as the reference. $[0/90_4]_s$ is used to observe the effect of thickness of transverse ply, i.e. "Thickness effect", while $[0_4/90]_s$ is used to study the effect of thickness of the $[0]$ constraining ply, i.e. "Constraint effect".

Finally, tensile samples with the dimensions illustrated in Figure 1 (right) are cut from the resulting laminates and tabbed with 20 x 20 [mm] Glass-Epoxy tabs.

Figure 1: (Left) Thermal program used to prepare laminates with two different cooling rates. (Right) Description of tensile samples.

3 EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

Tests were conducted on Instron 5882 tensile machine. Longitudinal axial strain was measured using Video Extensometer. Two types of tensile tests were conducted: The first is direct quasi-static tensile test with displacement control until failure. The second is Load-Unload quasi-static tensile test with displacement control from 0 to 2 [mm] with an increment of 0.2 [mm], i.e. 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 ... 2.0 [mm], where 0.2 mm would correspond to approximately 0.003 % strain. Same displacement levels were applied to all samples and the corresponding strain levels varied based on configuration. Loading speed for all tests was 0.5 [mm/min], and no waiting time was applied between unloading and loading cycles.

Figure 2: Stress-Strain curves of direct quasi-static tensile testing on [0/90]_s (up), [0/90₄]_s (center), and [0₄/90]_s (bottom). No clear difference was observed between samples prepared with fast and slow cooling.

3.1 Direct quasi-static tensile testing

Two samples of each configuration of each cooling rate were tested, in total 12 samples. The resulting Stress-Strain curves are presented in Figure 2. All samples of $[0/90]_s$ and $[0/90_4]_s$ failed catastrophically. On the other hand, $[0_4/90]_s$ didn't reach failure due to slippage of tabs. The authors are working on preparing longer samples with longer gripping area (but same grip to grip distance) to solve this issue.

Since fibers are the main load carrier in the composite, Stiffness and Strength are expected to be dependent on the ratio of $[0]$ plies in the cross-ply, which is clearly evident in the plots in Figure 2 (Strength of $[0_4/90]$ was not reached).

On the other hand, no difference could be seen between samples of different cooling rates (more samples are planned for testing in order to get statistically representative results and determine the normal scatter of data). Similarity between fast and slow cooled samples can be simply due to the fact that in such sample configuration the load is almost completely carried by the $[0]$ fibers that any difference in matrix properties is not noticeable.

Table 1 lists the values of Initial Stiffness, Strength, and Strain at failure of the 12 samples. Initial Stiffness is calculated at 0.1 % strain.

Sample Code	Config.	Cooling Rate	Stiffness [GPa]	Strength [MPa]	Strain @ failure
<i>FA-1</i>	$[0/90]_s$	fast	20.3	379	2.24
<i>FA-2</i>		fast	19.0	278	2.06
<i>SA-1</i>		slow	21.0	303	1.94
<i>SA-2</i>		slow	17.5	279	2.14
<i>FC-1</i>	$[0/90_4]_s$	fast	9.6	128	2.14
<i>FC-2</i>		fast	10.6	128	1.87
<i>SC-1</i>		slow	10.2	127	2.22
<i>SC-2</i>		slow	10.4	145	2.20
<i>FE-1</i>	$[0_4/90]_s$	fast	24.7	N/A	N/A
<i>FE-2</i>		fast	31.2	N/A	N/A
<i>SE-1</i>		slow	30.4	N/A	N/A
<i>SE-2</i>		slow	26.7	N/A	N/A

Table 1: Mechanical properties of direct quasi-static tensile testing of fast and slow cooled samples.

3.2 Load-Unload quasi-static tensile testing

One sample of each configuration of each cooling rate was tested, in total 6 samples. Figure 3 shows an example of the loading cycles for the sample $[0/90_4]$ Fast (FC-3). At each cycle, stiffness was calculated at the unload stage to observe stiffness degradation. The final results for all samples are demonstrated in Figure 4. As expected, stiffness value is dominated by the ratio of $[0]$ plies in the cross-ply. The rate of degradation was not included here, but it can be noticed that samples with high $[0]$ content hardly show any degradation, while those with high $[90]$ content show clear degradation, which is expected considering that plastic deformation or damage occurs mainly in the matrix material not the fibers. Further it should be noted that "degradation" may be due to visco-elastic material behavior, so it is difficult to assign any material degradation to the results.

As in direct tensile tests, there was no clear difference between fast and slow cooled samples (more samples are planned for testing in order to get statistically representative results and determine the normal scatter of data).

Figure 3: One example of load-unload cycles of [0/90₄] Fast (FC-3).

Figure 4: Stiffness degradation for load-unload quasi-static testing of all samples. Again no clear trend could be observed between fast and slow cooled samples.

4 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Cross-ply samples prepared with different constraint ratios and cooling rates were tensile tested to observe the effect on the mechanical behaviour and damage of the material. Two types of tensile testing were carried out: Direct and Load-Unload. From direct tensile testing it was observed that Stiffness and Strength values depend mainly on the ratio of [0] plies in the laminate since fibres are the main load carrier. However, no difference was detected between fast and slow cooled samples. Similarly, in load-unload testing stiffness was dependent also on [0] plies ratio, and again no clear trend could be noticed between fast and slow cooled samples. The similarity between fast and slow cooling might be due to the fact that in such sample configuration [0] plies carry all the load overcoming any difference in matrix material.

Future work to be published soon [7] include testing of more samples to produce statistically representative results, and defining a proper approach to characterize damage mechanisms and detect the initiation point and progression of damage and their dependence on constraint ratio and cooling rate.

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